

Influence of Dilution on the Molecular Refractivities of Complex Cyanides and Cobalt Amines.

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It has long been known that the refractivity of inorganic salts in the solid state is approximately equal to that of their dilute solutions (Heydweiller, *Ann. Physik*, 1913, **41**, 520; *Physikal. Z.*, 1925, **26**, 526), and Fajans and Kohner, (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, **A**, **147**, 241) when the salts are split up completely into ions and their refractivities behave strictly in an additive manner. Prominent workers in course of their investigations have, however, made many anomalous observations where the values of the molecular refractivity were not strictly additive; neither there was a regular order of variation in the molecular refractivities of many simple inorganic salts as the dilution was progressively altered. With a view to study the behaviour of the complex inorganic molecules with regard to their molecular refractivity at various dilutions (namely concentrations), a series of experiments was carried out by means of a Pulfrich refractometer and the results, calculated from the observations made under uniform conditions as far as possible, are being communicated through this paper for publication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Pure salts of complex cyanides and cobalt amines were taken and their standard solutions in terms of molecular concentration were prepared. The solutions being thus prepared were poured in the small cup of the refractometer and the readings for the refractive index of the yellow line were taken; the apparatus had been previously corrected for its zero error and a helium tube was excited by an induction coil to produce a continuous and prominent yellow ray for measuring the refractivities of the substances. Readings on the circular disc, which was graduated in degrees and minutes after zero error connection, gave the refractive value of the solution directly on consulting a table supplied by the manufacturers. The refractivity of the salts at several dilutions was thus determined and later on their molecular refractivity was calculated by multiplying the specific refractivity of the dissolved salt with the molecular weight. Specific refractivity was calculated by applying the Lorenz-Lorenz formula as appears in the text books.

FIG. 1.

Curves 1—5 refer respectively to $K_4Cr(CN)_6$, $K_3Fe(CN)_6$, $K_3Co(CN)_6$, $K_2Ni(CN)_4$ and $K_2Pd(CN)_4$.

FIG. 2.

1—5 refer respectively to $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, $K_2Pt(CN)_4$ and KCN.

FIG. 3.

1—4 refer respectively to $K_4Os(CN)_6$, $K_4Ru(CN)_6$, $K_3Ir(CN)_6$ and $K_3Rh(CN)_6$.

FIG 4.

1-4 refer respectively to $[\text{CoEn}]_3\text{Cl}_3$, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6](\text{NH}_3)_3$, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NO}_2)]\text{Cl}_2$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}]\text{SO}_4$

FIG 5.

1-6 refer respectively to $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2)_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$, HCl , $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{Br}_2]\text{Br}$; $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NO}_2)](\text{NO}_3)_2$, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$; $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}]\text{SeO}_4$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{SCN})]\text{SeO}_4$

Theory.

According to the electromagnetic theory of light both atoms and ions experience an analogous polarisation in the homogeneous electric field waves. This action of light upon the atom is accompanied by a reaction of the atom on the light waves which cause a decrease in the velocity of their propagation, or in other words, the light ray is refracted. H. A. Lorenz has shown that there is a proportionality between the measure of polarisability of a particle and its molecular refractivity for long light waves and on the basis of theoretical considerations deduced the following expression for molecular refractivity

$$M. R. = \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{M}{d}$$

where M is the molecular weight, n , the refractive index, and d , the density of the substance; and the specific refractivity, R_s of the solution is given by

$$\frac{n_s^2 - 1}{n_s^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{1}{d_s}$$

The specific refractivity of the salt in solution has been calculated from the formula, $100 \nu_s = (r_w \times \% \text{ water}) + (r_{\text{salt}} \times \% \text{ salt})$, which when more elaborately expressed assumes the following forms,

$$R_{\text{salt}} = \frac{n_s^2 - 1}{n_s^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{1}{d_s} \cdot \frac{100}{P} - \left[\frac{n_w^2 - 1}{n_w^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{1}{d_w} \right] \frac{100 - P}{P},$$

where n_s denotes the refractive index of the solution at the observed temperature, d_s , the density of the solution at the observed temp., P , percentage of the salt in the solution by weight, and n_w , d_w are the refractive index of water and density respectively at the observed temperature.

*Molecular Refractivities of Complex Cyanides at 21°
under several Dilutions.*

TABLE I.

Refractive index of distilled water at 21° = 1.3328.

Conc. of the soln.	Density of the soln.	Percentage strength of the soln.	Refractive index for yellow ray.	Refractivity		M. R_{∞} .
				Specific.	Molecular.	
$K_4Fe(CN)_6, 3H_2O.$						
M/11.5	1.0208	3.611	1.3391	0.171	62.11	62.1
M/57.5	1.0026	0.7347	1.3339	0.140	51.56	
M/115	1.0004	0.3682	1.3331	0.120	44.19	
$K_4Pt(CN)_4.$						
M/10	1.0207	3.6978	1.3359	0.126	47.55	47.5
M/50	1.0023	0.7537	1.3333	0.120	45.30	
M/100	1.0005	0.3772	1.3329	0.090	33.97	
$K_2Pd(CN)_4, 3H_2O.$						
M/10	1.0152	3.3783	1.3364	0.178	51.42	51.4
M/50	1.0016	0.6848	1.3337	0.170	49.12	
M/100	0.9999	0.3429	1.3334	0.140	40.45	
KCN.						
M/10	1.0009	0.6540	1.3333	0.150	9.76	
M/50	0.9987	0.1303	1.3331	0.200	13.02	13.00
M/100	0.9985	0.0652	1.3330	0.200	13.02	

TABLE I (contd.).

Conc. of the soln.	Density of the soln.	Percentage strength of the soln.	Refractive index for yellow ray.	Refractivity Specific.	Refractivity Molecular.	M. R. _∞
K₃Fe(CN)₆.						
<i>M/10</i>	1·0161	3·2403	1·3378	0·177	58·28	58·3
<i>M/50</i>	1·0018	0·6573	1·3340	0·170	55·97	
<i>M/100</i>	1·00002	0·3292	1·3335	0·160	52·67	
<i>M/500</i>	0·9986	0·0659	1·3330	0·100	32·92	
K₂Ni(CN)₄.						
<i>M/10</i>	1·0112	2·3827	1·3381	0·213	51·32	53·00
<i>M/50</i>	1·0008	0·4814	1·3336	0·220	53·00	
<i>M/100</i>	0·9995	0·2410	1·3335	0·180	43·36	
<i>M/500</i>	0·9985	0·0482	1·3330	0·100	24·09	
K₃Co(CN)₆.						
<i>M/10</i>	1·0177	3·6498	1·3378	0·170	56·47	56·5
<i>M/50</i>	1·0021	0·7413	1·3340	0·160	53·15	
<i>M/100</i>	1·0002	0·3714	1·3335	0·170	56·47	
<i>M/500</i>	0·9986	0·07439	1·3330	0·100	33·22	
K₄Cr(CN)₆.						
<i>M/10</i>	1·0165	3·5854	1·3377	0·176	64·15	64·1
<i>M/50</i>	1·0019	0·7276	1·3339	0·170	61·96	
<i>M/100</i>	1·00006	0·3644	1·3335	0·170	61·96	
<i>M/500</i>	0·9985	0·07300	1·3329	0·100	36·45	

TABLE II.

Temperature = 27·4°.

K₃Rh(CN)₆.						
<i>M/10</i>	1·0174	3·6980	1·33698	0·165	62·20	62·2
<i>M/50</i>	1·0004	0·7519	1·3327	0·162	60·96	
<i>M/100</i>	0·9983	0·3769	1·3323	0·175	65·85	
<i>M/500</i>	0·9966	0·0755	1·3318	0·155	58·32	
K₃Ir(CN)₆.						
<i>M/10</i>	1·0267	4·543	1·3372	0·1394	65·03	65·0
<i>M/50</i>	1·0023	0·9309	1·33036	0·1435	66·94	
<i>M/100</i>	0·9992	0·4668	1·3324	0·147	68·57	
<i>M/500</i>	0·9968	0·0936	1·3319	0·145	67·64	

TABLE II (contd.).

Conc. of the soln.	Density of the soln.	Percentage str. of the solution.	Refractive index for yellow ray.	Refractivity		M. R. _∞
				Specific.	Molecular.	
$K_4Ru(CN)_6$.						
M/10	1.0241	4.572	1.3394	0.1734	71.81	71.8
M/50	1.0018	0.9346	1.3335	0.1870	77.45	
M/100	0.9990	0.4686	1.3326	0.1820	75.39	
M/500	0.9967	0.09396	1.3319	0.160	66.27	
$K_4Os(CN)_6$.						
M/10	1.0341	5.391	1.3408	0.1564	78.72	78.7
M/50	1.0038	1.111	1.3336	0.1590	80.04	
M/100	0.9999	0.5573	1.3328	0.1680	84.57	
M/500	0.9969	0.1118	1.3319	0.1400	70.47	

Molecular Refractivities of Complex Cobalt Ammine Salts at 30°.

TABLE III.

Refractive index of distilled water at 30° determined by the refractometer = 1.3317 for yellow ray.

Conc. of the soln.	Density of the soln.	Percentage strength of the soln.	Refractive index for yellow ray.	Refractivity		M.R. _∞
				Specific.	Molecular.	
$[Co(NH_3)_6]Cl_3$.						
M/50	0.9985	0.6916	1.3331	0.241	83.26	83.3
M/100	0.9971	0.3463	1.3324	0.244	84.29	
M/250	0.9762	0.1387	1.3319	0.260	89.82	
M/500	0.9959	0.0693	1.3318	0.350	120.92	
$[Co(NH_3)_6](NO_3)_2$.						
M/50	0.9992	0.6944	1.3329	0.203	70.43	70.4
M/250	0.9964	0.1393	1.3319	0.230	79.80	
M/500	0.9960	0.0695	1.3318	0.265	91.95	
$[Co(NH_3)_5NO_3]Cl_2$.						
M/50	0.9988	0.5546	1.3329	0.216	59.81	59.8
M/250	0.9963	0.1112	1.3319	0.250	69.22	
M/500	0.9960	0.0556	1.3318	0.280	77.53	

TABLE III(contd.).

Conc. of the soln.	Density of the soln.	Percentage strength of the soln.	Refractive index for yellow ray.	Refractivity.		M. R_{∞} .
				Specific.	Molecular.	
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ NO ₃] [NO ₃] ₂ .						
M/100	0.9974	0.3308	1.3322	0.196	64.67	64.7
M/250	0.9964	0.1325	1.3319	0.225	74.24	
M/500	0.9960	0.06626	1.3318	0.265	87.44	
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ Cl]Cl ₂ .						
M/100	0.9967	0.2513	1.3322	0.253	63.34	63.8
M/250	0.9961	0.1005	1.3319	0.290	72.60	
M/500	0.9959	0.0503	1.3318	0.330	82.60	
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ Cl]SeO ₄ .						
M/136.8	0.9973	0.3309	1.3321	0.182	58.72	58.7
M/250	0.9966	0.1813	1.33187	0.190	61.29	
M/500	0.9961	0.0907	1.3318	0.225	72.59	
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ (SCN)]SeO ₄ .						
M/150	0.9976	0.2305	1.3321	0.145	50.05	50.0
M/250	0.9968	0.1384	1.33187	0.150	51.77	
M/500	0.9962	0.06926	1.3318	0.210	72.48	
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ Cl]SO ₄ .						
M/50	0.9988	0.5535	1.3326	0.186	51.42	51.4
M/100	0.9972	0.2772	1.3322	0.202	55.84	
M/250	0.9963	0.11097	1.33187	0.230	63.58	
M/500	0.9960	0.05506	1.3318	0.280	77.40	
[Co(NH ₃) ₄ SO ₄]HISO ₄ .						
M/100	0.9973	0.3379	1.3326	0.201	67.73	67.7
M/250	0.9963	0.1352	1.33187	0.220	74.13	
M/500	0.9960	0.06763	1.3318	0.270	90.98	
[Co(NH ₃) ₄ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₃ .						
M/100	0.9971	0.2809	1.3322	0.209	58.72	
M/250	0.9962	0.1125	1.33187	0.250	70.24	
[Co(NH ₃) ₄ (NO ₂) ₂]Cl.						
M/20	1.0021	1.270	1.3344	0.222	56.48	56.5
M/50	0.9982	0.5098	1.3327	0.224	56.99	
M/100	0.9968	0.2552	1.3322	0.235	59.79	
M/250	0.9962	0.1021	1.33187	0.250	63.60	

TABLE III (contd.).

Conc of the soln	Density of the solution	Percentage strength of soln.	Refractive index for yellow ray.	Specific Refractivity	Molecular Refractivity	M R _∞
[Co(NH ₃) ₄ (NO ₂) ₂](SeO ₄) _{1/2}						
M/50	1.0004	0.7240	1.3326	0.148	53.60	53.60
M/100	0.9980	0.3629	1.3322	0.157	56.86	
M/250	0.9964	0.1454	1.3316	0.210	76.05	
M/500	0.9961	0.0727	1.3318	0.240	86.92	
[Co(NH ₃) ₄ C ₂ O ₄]Cl.						
M/100	0.9967	0.2512	1.3321	0.227	56.84	
M/250	0.9961	0.1005	1.3318	0.230	57.59	
[Co(NH ₃) ₄ Br ₂]Br.						
M/200	0.9967	0.1840	1.3319	0.190	69.68	69.5
M/250	0.9964	0.1472	1.33187	0.200	73.35	
M/500	0.9961	0.0736	1.3318	0.240	88.0	
[Co{C ₂ H ₄ (NH ₃) ₂ }] ₂ Cl ₂]Cl, HCl, 2H ₂ O.						
M/100	0.9972	0.3589	1.3325	0.254	90.88	90.9
M/250	0.9962	0.1436	1.3319	0.250	89.45	
M/500	0.9960	0.0718	1.3318	0.270	96.61	
[Co(NH ₃) ₄ (H ₂ O)Cl]SeO ₄						
M/150	0.9963	0.2166	1.3321	0.265	85.76	85.7
M/250	0.9960	0.1300	1.33187	0.270	87.38	
M/500	0.9958	0.0651	1.3318	0.310	100.32	
[Co(NH ₃) ₄ CO ₃]NO ₃ , 1/2 H ₂ O						
M/50	0.9979	0.5170	1.3325	0.212	54.69	54.7
M/100	0.9968	0.2588	1.3321	0.217	55.98	
M/250	0.9961	0.1036	1.3318	0.225	58.04	
[Co(NH ₃) ₄ CO ₃]Cl.						
M/50	0.9972	0.4461	1.3325	0.245	54.49	54.5
M/100	0.9964	0.2232	1.3321	0.251	55.83	
M/250	0.9960	0.0893	1.33187	0.310	68.95	
M/500	0.9958	0.0446	1.3318	0.390	86.74	
[Co(NH ₃) ₄ CO ₃] ₂ SO ₄ , 3H ₂ O.						
M/50	1.0014	1.046	1.3334	0.188	98.50	
M/100	0.9985	0.5247	1.3327	0.208	108.98	?
M/250	0.9968	0.2102	1.3320	0.208	108.98	
M/500	0.9962	0.1052	1.3318	0.210	110.03	
[Co(NH ₃) ₄ CO ₃] ₂ SeO ₄ , 3H ₂ O.						
M/50	1.0021	1.1400	1.3335	0.185	105.66	
M/100	0.9989	0.5717	1.3327	0.194	110.80	?
M/250	0.9969	0.2291	1.3320	0.201	114.80	
M/500	0.9963	0.1146	1.3318	0.190	106.62	

DISCUSSION.

The foregoing tables show that the complex cyanogen salts may be classified into two main classes with regard to their behaviour towards refraction of light on progressive dilution of the salts.

(i) Some salts among those which have been investigated show a gradual diminution of molecular refractivity as the dilution of the solution is increased.

(ii) While others show a gradual rise in the value of their molecular refractivity with dilution. Compounds like potassium ferrocyanide, platinocyanide, palladocyanide, rhodicyanide, ferricyanide, nickelocyanide, and chromicyanide show a gradual fall in molecular refractivity with dilution, while potassiumiridi, rutheno, and osmo cyanides have a tendency to show an increase up to a certain dilution. It appears from this behaviour of the cyanides that the variation of refractivity is connected also with the stable or unstable nature of the complex among other plausible factors on which the refractivity of the salts depends in general, *e.g.*, ionisation, and molecular concentration,

FIG. 6.

FIG. 8.

1-2 refer respectively to $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2]\text{Cl}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2](\text{SeO}_4)_3$.

FIG. 7.

1-3 refer respectively to $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{CO}_3]_2\text{SeO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{CO}_3]_2 \cdot \text{SO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{CO}_3]\text{NO}_3 \cdot \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$

FIG. 9.

1-2 refer respectively to $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]\text{SeO}_4$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{SO}_4]\text{HSO}_4$.

etc. The gradual diminution of molecular refractivity on dilution seems to be a normal behaviour of the complex salt, for with increasing dilution the intensity of the ionic field will be gradually weakened due to the progressive hydration of the heavily charged trivalent or quadrivalent complex ions. Dipole-water molecules under such conditions will form layers, masking the charged ions to a considerable extent which will result in correspondingly lowering the molecular refractivities of such complex salts under investigation. The gradual increase of molecular refractivity on dilutions seems to be an abnormal behaviour of the complex molecules and this may be ascribed to the gradual decomposition of the complex ions, into simpler ions whereby the electric field of the solution is intensified causing an increase in the molecular refractivity of the salts at a higher dilution. Complex iridium, ruthenium and osmium cyanides are of heavy metals and may, therefore, have a tendency to form comparatively less stable cyanide complexes than those of elements which are lighter; hence, the behaviour of the complex cyanides of these elements is opposite to that of other cyanides which appear in the tables.

Variation of the molecular refractivities of cobalt complex salts with dilution follow a more or less regular order. Almost all of these salts show a gradual increase of refractivity on dilution for which the instability of the cobalt complex radical seems to be responsible. In view of the above observations it may be further suggested that in the case of such complex salts as are comparatively less stable, the changes of molecular refractivity on dilution may furnish a suitable method for determining the degree of stability of the complex ion of the salt.

Molecular refractivities for red ray from an excited hydrogen tube were also observed, which presented rather anomalous variations with abrupt increase or decrease in the middle of the series of dilution. Such abrupt variations of a discontinuous nature suggest the possible formation of hydration compounds or decomposition of the complex salt.

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